

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF A COMPOSITE MADE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL ALFA FIBERS

Sami. Ben Brahim, Ridha. Ben Cheikh

*Unité de Recherche Synthèse et Analyse des Matériaux,
Department of Industrial Engineering,
Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs de Tunis, BP37, Le Belvédère, Tunisia*

SUMMARY: We present in this contribution the study of the mechanical properties in traction of a structural composite material reinforced with a natural fiber called the Alfa fiber. The structural composite is a laminate reinforced with Alfa fibers unidirectional plies bound together with Polyester matrix. The first section of this work consists in presenting the mechanical behavior of the long Alfa fibers based on some experiments that we carry out. In the second, section we focus on the mechanical properties of the composite with respect to fibers filling ratio and fibers orientation.

KEYWORDS: Alfa fibers, natural fiber, polyester composite, unidirectional reinforced composites, composite work up.

INTRODUCTION

Alfa fibres are natural fibres extracted from the plant *Stippa Tenacissima*, widely cultivated in North Africa and specially in Tunisia. They are used since many centuries in textile and ropes. In these last years many new applications of Alfa Fibres in the field of non-structural composites materials are described, in which short Alfa fibres are used in random to reinforce thermoset and thermoplastic materials [1-3]. The aim of this work is to study the mechanical behaviour of a new structural thermoset composite, reinforced with long unidirectional Alfa fibres, perfectly arranged with highly filling ratio and drown in a polyester matrix.

Study of the mechanical behaviour of the long Alfa fibres

The long Alfa fibers are extracted from the Alfa stem by the soda process which consists in cooking the plant stem in 3N NaOH solution during 2 hours in the atmospheric pressure at 100°C and in bleaching them in a 40% NaClO solution during 1 hour. The obtained fibers are washed abundantly with water and dried at 60°C during 6 hours. The Alfa fibers are then carded to be soft and separated. This extraction method was optimized to get long Alfa fibers specially used for the reinforcement of composite materials [2].

The extracted long Alfa fibers have a density of 1.4 according to the standard NF T 20-053 [4], an average length of 350mm according to the standard ISO 2602 [5], a linear mass of 2.7 tex According to the standard ISO1973 [6] and a cross section area average of 19.10-3mm². The long Alfa fibers have a Kappa index of 20.6 according to the standard ISO 302 [7]. The Kappa index gives the degree of lignin that cellulosic fibers may contain after a soda extraction. The Kappa index varies widely with the extraction parameters.

The mechanical properties in traction of the long Alfa fibers are determined experimentally, according to the standard ISO 1963 [8]. The measurements are realized with a strain speed of 15mm/min using a single column Lloyd traction machine equipped with 1KN measuring cell. This speed was chosen in order to get a global test time of 20 ± 3 seconds according to the same standard. The distance between the clips is 250mm.

The tested fibers were not conditioned and the measurements were performed in the atmospheric conditions. We realized 50 measurements. The obtained results are presented in the table 1.

According to the literature [9], the mechanical performance of the Alfa fibers are close to those of sisal, jute, flax and hemp. The ramie fiber remains the strongest natural one. Besides, the specific Young modulus of this fiber is similar to the modulus of some synthetic fibers such as glass fibers. However, the measured stress at failure on synthetic fibers is more important than the one measured on natural fibers.

Table 1: Mechanical properties in traction of the long Alfa fibers

	Average value	Variation ratio (%)	Confidence interval at 95%
Young Modulus (GPa)	21,5	18	[18,2 ; 24,7]
Stress at failure (MPa)	247	29	[187 ; 306]
Strain at failure (%)	1,96	27	[1,50 ; 2,40]

Study of the mechanical properties of the composite

Process of manufacturing the Alfa fibers structural composite

The first step of the composite manufacturing process consists in arranging the fibers in unidirectional cloths before soaking them with resin. It's a manual operation where the long Alfa fibers are fixed on two double face tapes glued on the extremity of a sheet of metal and distant with the required cloth length. The fibers are fixed on the tape as uniform as possible and parallel to the required direction

The realized cloths are hard to handle and risk to disperse since they are not woven. To avoid this problem, the Alfa fibers were bound together with a starch aqueous solution of 20g/l in order to get uniform and homogeneous cloths. An amount of 1 liter of starch solution per square meter of Alfa fibers cloth was used to soak the fibers. The fibers were then pressed between two metallic plates in order to get thin and uniform cloths and stewed at 80°C for 2 hours.

In this way, we obtain unidirectional natural cloths with long Alfa fibers perfectly arranged and easy to handle and work with. We produced different unidirectional Alfa cloths with different fibers angles, having weights varying between 280 and 360g/m².

With the obtained unidirectional Alfa fibers cloths, we manufactured the structural composite. The manufacturing process consists in soaking 1, 2, 3 or 4 unidirectional Alfa fiber plies with polyester resin in the mould impression then to press them with the mould cover.

Mechanical properties of the Alfa/Polyester composite

The studied mechanical properties of the composite are those given by traction. The constitutive law of a composite material, made of unidirectional fibres, under a load in the same direction as the reinforcement, can be formulated as a plane problem characterised by the two Young modulus E_1 and E_2 , the Poisson coefficient ν_{12} and the shear modulus G_{12} . Where 1 represents the fibre direction and 2 the orthogonal direction.

The elasticity modulus E_1 and E_2 are given by traction experiments in direction 1 and 2. The determination of Poisson coefficient ν_{12} is given by the same test but using a special gauge able to give the deformation in both directions 1 and 2. Finally the calculation of the shear modulus G_{12} is given by traction experiments on composites with fibres oriented differently from the load direction.

Table 2 gives the mechanical properties in traction of the Polyester/Alfa composite realised according to the standard ISO 527-5 [10] on specimens with 45% of fibre filling ratio.

Table 2. Mechanical properties in traction of the Polyester/Alfa composite

	Average value	Variation ratio (%)	Confidence interval at 95%
Young modulus E_1 (GPa)	12,3	3%	[11,9 ; 12,7]
Young modulus E_2 (GPa)	5	4%	[4,8 ; 5,2]
Shear modulus G_{12} (MPa)	2.47	6%	[2.4 ; 2.54]
Poisson coefficient ν_{12}	0,362	2.5%	[0,352 ; 0,371]

The determination of the four parameters E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} and ν_{12} allows the calculation of the stiffness matrix of the composite, and consequently the material constitutive law. This constitutive law gives the response of the Polyester/Alfa composite to any biaxial load.

Effects of the fibers filling ratio

The second part of the experiments concerns the study of the influence of the fibers filling ratio V_f on the composite mechanical properties. For this purpose we manufactured different samples of Polyester/Alfa composites with different volume filling ratio. All the composites are made of unidirectional Alfa fibers oriented in the same direction as the traction load. For each series of samples, we measured, according to the standards ISO 527-5 [10], the Young modulus E_1 , the stress σ_1 and the strain ε_1 . The obtained results are shown in table 3. The number of samples for each series is six.

Table 3: The influence of the fibers filling ratio on the composite mechanical properties

V_f (%)	E_1 (GPa)	σ_1 (MPa)	ε_1 (%)
0	4,1	64	2,7
12	6,6	75	2.3
21	8,2	96	2.3
32	10,2	118	2.6
44	12,3	149	3.1

We calculated the specific Young modulus E_1 for both Alfa and glass fibres, estimated for a fibre filling ratio of 40%, we obtained 8GPa for the first material and 12GPa for the second one. This means that for the same material weight, the glass composite is one time and a half stiffer than the Alfa composite, so it is possible to use Alfa fibres as reinforcement for structural parts as well as glass fibres.

Effects of the fibers orientation

The third part of the experiments concerns the study the influence of the fibers orientation on the composite mechanical properties. For this purpose, we manufactured different samples of Polyester/Alfa composites with different fibers orientation. All the composites are made of unidirectional Alfa fibers with a volume filling ratio of 45%. For each series of samples, we measured according to the standards ISO 527-5 [10] the Young modulus $E_{I\alpha}$, the Poisson ratio $\nu_{I,II\alpha}$ and the stress $\sigma_{I\alpha}$ where (I) is the load direction, (II) is the orthogonal direction and α is the angle between the fibers and the load direction. The obtained results corresponding to six samples are given in table 4.

Table 4: The influence of fibers orientation on the composite mechanical properties

α	$E_{I\alpha}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{I,II\alpha}$	$\sigma_{I\alpha}$ (MPa)
0°	12.3	0.362	150
10°	11.5	0.364	104
30°	8.1	0.365	43
45°	6.4	0.297	33
90°	5	0.147	18

If we compare the experimental results to the theoretical evolution given by literature [11, 12], we can notice that the experimental and theoretical evolutions have the same shape for both Young modulus $E_{I\alpha}$ and the Poisson ratio $\nu_{I,II\alpha}$. However, for the Young modulus, there is an increasing difference between the theoretical and experimental values for α angles up to 15° . This difference is probably due to the anisotropy of the Alfa fibers since the theoretical expression doesn't take into account the fibers anisotropy and is available only for isotropic reinforcement. The same differences are shown on the experimental and theoretical Poisson ratio evolution and are principally due to the fibers anisotropy.

CONCLUSION

The reinforcement of composite material with natural fibers seems to be very interesting in the design of structural parts. Alfa fibers can contribute to the resistance and stiffness of composite materials as well as synthetic fibers such as E-glass fibers. This has an important economical and ecological impact since Alfa fibers are natural, ecological, biodegradable and renewable. Among the composites applications where we can use the Alfa fibers, we can mention some aerodynamics car parts such as deflectors, wings or wheel houses. We can also mention the sport fields and specially kite surf boards which represent nowadays a sport in full expansion and requires light strong and cheap reinforcements. However, we still have difficulties to explore Alfa fibers mainly because of their poor aptitude to be woven in machine.

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